

This War of Mine

Developed by: 11 bit studios

Article contributed by: Lucian Alikhani

Keywords

Civilian Perspectives on War, Death, Empathy, History, Human Rights Education, Military Ethics, Psychology, Strategic Decision-making

Figure 1. Screenshot from *This War of Mine* (11 bit studios, 2014). Used under fair use for academic purposes.

Introduction

This War of Mine (TWOM, see Figure 1) is a 2D survival game where players manage civilians in a besieged city, focusing on the human cost of war. Instead of heroic soldiers, players experience starvation, fear, and moral ambiguity from a civilian perspective. Survival requires balancing needs, health, and morale while scavenging for supplies amid threats. Inspired by the Siege of Sarajevo, the game offers a bleak, authentic experience to provoke reflection on war by confronting players with their own emotions (Maiberg, 2014; Hutchinson, 2019). Its visuals and ethical dilemmas make it suitable for use in conflict studies, psychology, or ethics courses for mature audiences. Considered a serious game, it fosters empathy and critical thinking about humanitarian crises. It is available on PC, consoles, and mobile devices since its 2014 release.

Facts

Release date: First release in 2014 (PC). Later console/mobile ports; major “Final Cut” update released in 2019.

Developer: 11 bit studios

Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	Single player
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	Flexible. A meaningful session can be ~45–90 minutes; a single game play typically spans several hours and may take a full day.
Languages:	Multilingual UI/subtitles (e.g., English, German, Polish, French, and others). Minimal voice lines (primarily Polish) with subtitles available.
Environment:	PC or console (Windows/macOS/Linux versions available; also PlayStation/Xbox/Switch/mobile ports). Requires a quiet setting; headphones recommended. For classroom use, either individual play (one device per student/group) or facilitator-led play via projector/screen.
Material:	No physical materials required beyond the device and the installed game. Optional: controller on consoles; instructor-created worksheets/discussion prompts for teaching contexts.
Price:	Paid commercial title (base game with optional DLC/editions). The exact price varies by platform, region, and sales (for example, in Germany on 14 August 2025, the game for a computer is around 18 euros, while it is approximately 4 euros for a mobile phone).

Resonance & Criticism

Since 2014, TWOM has been widely recognised in the games and education sectors. It won the IGF Audience Award (2015) and the SXSW Matthew Crump Cultural Innovation Award (2015); by 2019, it had sold over 4.5 million copies across PC and consoles (2015 Finalists & Winners, 2015; Gamespresso, 2015; Jones, 2019). In 2020, Poland added the game to the national school reading list (Tilles, 2020). Some critics, however, argue that the game's unrelenting bleakness is depressing and that its mechanics simplify complex issues, including depression (Kaar, 2018).

Game Principle & Process

The game is played from a side-on cross-section of a ruined house in the fictional city of Pogoren. Players control multiple civilians with different skills, personalities, and needs. During the day, players manage their shelter, craft furniture, cook food, and tend to the sick or wounded. At night, they send characters to scavenge locations for vital supplies, facing risks from soldiers, looters, and desperate civilians. The characters can also remain in their shelter to guard or sleep. Each choice for the night has consequences for the characters' well-being and the story's unfolding.

The game lacks a win condition beyond survival. Characters can die, become depressed, or abandon the group. Moral choices (e.g., refusing help to others) shape the emotional state of

characters and, by that, influence the ending. The mechanics incorporate permadeath, limited resources, and emotional status bars (hungry, sad, sick, tired). The game was developed based on the real testimonies from the Siege of Sarajevo (Kaar, 2018).

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

TWOM was not developed as an educational game; however, several clear educational objectives have been identified. These include: helping players gain an understanding of war from a civilian's perspective (Bos, 2021); practising ethical reasoning in uncertain situations, where there are no simple solutions (Sayilgan, 2017); and encouraging a shift in perspective from heroism to care, with an emphasis on cooperation and managing vulnerability (Saklofske et al., 2019).

These objectives connect play to course debates in ethics, philosophy, history, and the social sciences. The game is already recommended for exactly these subjects in Poland's secondary education (This War of Mine, n.d.).

The character's needs in the face of constant resource scarcity, and elements such as irreversible death, mean players must make hard trade-offs, such as deciding who gets to eat or who takes the risk of scavenging. These decisions often involve morally difficult and high-stakes situations, for example, stealing from an elderly couple to feed your child and friends (Roy, 2016). Features like systems for fatigue and illness, dependency, and loss are elements that 11 bit studios deliberately designed to encourage moral reflection (de Smale et al., 2017). Together, these systems create moral tension and raise questions about care and justice without telling players what the "right" choice is (Roy, 2016; de Smale et al., 2017). The game also differs from previous war games by including children (since 2016, with The Little Ones DLC) who were previously absent from such games. This inclusion enables the game to portray a more realistic image of war (de Smale et al., 2017). The civilian focus and routine care tasks directly support learning about human dignity, vulnerability, and the social fabric under siege (Roy, 2016).

Debriefing is especially crucial in *This War of Mine* due to its emotionally charged scenarios and ethical ambiguity. Players often experience guilt, frustration, or moral dissonance after making survival decisions that harm others. A structured debrief allows learners to process these emotions and connect them to course concepts such as moral injury, empathy, or the ethics of care. Instructors might invite reflection on questions like: How did it feel to make choices that hurt others? What moral justifications did you use to decide who to help or harm? How do these feelings mirror real-world civilian dilemmas in war? Discussing these tensions helps transform emotional responses into critical understanding rather than mere distress. The role of the instructors, therefore, is to help students contextualise their emotional reactions within theories of moral judgment and empathy.

The game needs little tech training; the controls can be learned during class. Most of the time should go to discussion and reflection, not trying to “finish” the game, since a full playthrough of a story can take 2–15 hours.

Effectiveness

Evidence is still limited and mixed. In a medical school course, integrating the game prompted students to reflect on new perspectives on life in urban conflict and on their engagement with ethical dilemmas (Mishori et al., 2017). One small experiment showed no big change in empathy after a single session, but a slight improvement after several sessions (Wulansari et al., 2020). Analyses of player reviews further suggest the game often prompts reflection on civilian suffering and the moral complexity of war (Bos, 2021), though these results should be interpreted with caution. Moreover, there is still a need for controlled, long-term studies to examine the duration of the mentioned effects and their generalizability.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Because the game depicts starvation, violence, suicide, and mental illness, it may distress younger players or those with trauma histories. Its simplified handling of depression, where characters recover mood with food and sleep, may trivialise complex conditions (Kaar, 2018). The game forces players to make morally troubling choices that can provoke discomfort. Teachers should warn about sensitive content and offer support. It is not suitable for children and may be inaccessible for those with visual or motor impairments due to small icons.

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl, Johannes Katsarov

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